

A Study of Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary Grade Students in Garhbeta Block, Paschim Medinipur, WB.

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ABSTRACT

The present study tries to investigate the level emotional intelligence of XIth&XIIth grade school students of Garhbeta Block, Paschim Medinipur in West Bengal. Main purpose of this empirical study is examine of Emotional Intelligence of XIth &XIIth grade secondary students. For this study a standardised adopted Bengali version questionnaire developed by Sangyot Pethe, Anukul Hyde and Upindar Dhar consisting 34 items was used to collect data from the assigned two secondary schools. Each item of this questionnaire with five alternatives (like strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree) was employed. Only 114 XIth &XIIth grade students were assigned as samples. Purposive sampling procedure was used. For analysing the data, descriptive statistical techniques like SD, t- test were used. After analysing the collected data the result showed that APL and BPL, general and others, male and female of XIth&XIIth grade higher secondary students have insignificant difference in their emotional intelligence. Only Hindu and others religion students have significant difference exists between them with respect to emotional intelligence.

Introduction;

In present era, the importance of academic achievement plays a major role in the learning process of school children. A student's success in learning needs a proof, and academic achievement or more

particularly, the scores that the students obtain in different subject areas. In the past, it was thought that intellect had a direct impact on pupils' performance. If any students were found to be less intelligent, it has been found out by the researches that intelligence is not the single factors being responsible or influencing the achievement of student. Carroll, one of the associate of Benjamin Bloom postulated that student's learning are influenced by three factors – learner related variable, teacher related variable and situational variable .creative thinking ,emotional intelligence and adjustment are three independent variables taken by the present researcher coming under the learner related variable paradigm . Studies in the areas of academic achievement show that variable sex, SES, Intelligence, Emotional Intelligence and Creativity. Anxiety, self concept adjustment etc. affects that performance of students.

Education is a vital instrument for everyone to gain something distinct and to succeed in their lives. It is significant for both men and women. Each is vital to the growth of a prosperous and intelligent community. Since education gives people the ability to reach all of their strength and advancement, it will assist in transforming an individual into a better and more responsible citizen. The higher secondary level is a stage between primary and higher education where the student's physical, mental, social, and creative abilities develop rapidly. The major goal of higher secondary school education is to promote the holistic development of the student, enhance their intellectual, practical, and vocational abilities, as well as foster a scientific mindset and positive change in them. In addition to this, higher secondary education ought to be founded on a national curriculum framework (NCF), which includes a common core in addition to other adaptable elements.

Emotional Intelligence is one of the factor that greatly influence student's success. In 1993, Danniell Golman promoted the idea of Emotional Intelligence worldwide. A person's capacity to assess, control, and communicate their emotions in the most effective manner is known as emotional intelligence. It consists of four fundamental elements: self-awareness, self-motivation, empathy, and relationship management. "The ability to reason with emotion in four ways—perceiving emotion, integrating ideas, understanding emotion, and managing emotion—is a definition of emotion and intelligence.," according to Mayer and Salovey (1995).

Eva & Romoold (2006) demonstrated that kids that possess emotional intelligence see numerous improvements. Children with high emotional quotients (E.Q.) are more self-assured, have high self-esteem, have a positive attitude, and, most importantly are better learners, according to research. Emotional intelligence impacts our learning, relationships, health, and communication and shows the capacity to integrate empathy, intelligence, and emotions to comprehend thought. It is a meta-cognitive

ability of an individual that helps him or her to appraise, regulate and express one's emotion in the best possible way. It involves four basic components: Self awareness, motivating one self, empathy and handling relationship (Salovy & Mayer's 1990).

Significance of the study: G. Stanley Hall mentioned that adolescence is a period of "stress, strain, storm, and strife". Class XIth&XIIth higher secondary students belong to the 16- 18 years age group. The physical and mental development of adolescent children reaches such a level that they are no longer able to think about what they will and will not do. During this time, their mental stress is high, and they become rational. They are the future of the future society. They are going to sit in their second external examination of life. Emotional intelligence is the ability of a person which helps to manage situation, influence academic grades, interaction and adjustment in daily life. It reduces exam stress, anxiety and depression and get on with answering the questions. It handles own emotion and regulate others emotion and behavior. Emotional intelligence is crucial for students' self-regulation, improved academic performance, and provision of skills for both their personal and professional lives. It is evident from the explanation above that emotional intelligence aids a person in a variety of ways to succeed in life while preserving their happiness, education, and personal development. To determine how much emotional intelligence affects pupils academic performance or how much difference there is between them.

Review of the study: Review of the related literature helps to get clear concept and ideas about the present topic. It shows the right path and select suitable methodology for the study. Some studies are mentioned below-

Subramanyam, K. (2011) concluded that there is no significant difference with regard to the impact of gender on emotional intelligence and study skills of high school students.

Bhatnagar, A. and Mittal, A. (2010) revealed that student's birth order, gender and working status of mother's have impact on the student's emotional intelligence.

Gowdhaman, K. and Bala Murugan, M. (2010) revealed that Among the 11 study variables, emotional intelligence among B. Ed. teacher candidates is normal; however, gender, institution type, age, religion, type of management, family occupation, monthly income community, first-level degree, and entertainment all significantly affect emotional intelligence.

Kautish. P. (2010) opined that emotional intelligence skills have been strongly associated with dynamic leadership, satisfying personal life experiences and success in the workplace. This has resulted in calls for the incorporation of emotional intelligence competencies in university curricula to acquaint students with

emotional intelligence skills. It outlines recent research studying emotional intelligence in relation to university level students, and concludes with a call for university educators to integrate emotional intelligence skills in their courses across all levels.

Petrides et al. (2004) examined that emotional intelligence moderated the relationship between academic performance and cognitive ability.

Elder (1997) pointed out that emotions have a significant role in student's ability to learn content well, thus emotions can facilitate learning.

Statement of the Study:

Taking into consideration the above reviews title of the study may be stated as '**A Study of Emotional Intelligence of Higher Secondary Grade Students in Garhbeta Block, Paschim Medinipur, WB**'.

Objectives –

1. To find out status of emotional intelligence of XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students,
2. To find out the significant difference between Boys and girls XI & XIIth grade higher secondary school students towards emotional intelligence,
3. To find out the significant difference between APL and BPL XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students towards emotional intelligence,
4. To find out the significant difference between general and others XIth & XIIth higher grade secondary school students towards emotional intelligence,
5. To find out the significant difference exists between Hindu and others with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Hypothesis;

H01- There is no significant difference exists between boys and girls with respect to their emotional Intelligence.

H02- There is no significant difference exists between APL and BPL with respect to their emotional Intelligence.

H03- There is no significant difference exists between general and others with respect to their Emotional Intelligence.

H04- There is no significant difference exists between Hindu and others religion with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Delimitation of the study

1. Only 114 students were selected for the present study as sample.
2. This study was delimited only Bengali speaking students.
3. A standardized translated into Bengali version questionnaire was used to collect information from different XIth&XIIth grade higher secondary school students.
4. Only one psychological variable (Emotional Intelligence) was taken for the study.

Methodology of the Study:

Descriptive / survey method was used to study emotional intelligence among XIth &XIIth grade higher secondary school students.

Variable: The present study included the following variables:

Main variable-Emotional Intelligence (Independent Variable)

Background Variable -

- 1.Gender (Boys and Girls)
- 2.Economic status (APL and BPL)
- 3.Caste (General and Others)
- 4/ Religion (Hindu & Others)

Population: The population of the study is all secondary school students, West Bengal, India. Purposive sample technique was used to collect data for the study. Only114 students were taken for the study those who are studying in Bengali medium higher secondary school in Paschim Medinipur district affiliated from WBCHSE.

Sample: In the present study, a sample of 114 XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students from two schools were drawn. Purposive sampling procedure was employed to collect reliable data from the XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students.

Tool: Adopted and translated into Bengali version standardised 'Emotional Intelligence scale', developed by Sangot Pethe, Anukul Hyde and Upindar dhar was used to collect information from the XIth & XIIth grade secondary school students. Bengali version questionnaire consists 34 items with five alternatives.

Statistical techniques: Different statistical techniques like mean, SD, t- test were used to analyze the data.

Analysis and interpretation:

According to standardised emotional intelligence scale the level of XIth & XIIth secondary student are shown below

Category	Range	students	% of students
low	51 and above	21	18.43
Normal	52-84	65	57.01
High	85 above	28	24.56

Table-1- Descriptive statistic of selected variables are shown below

Variables	N	Mean	SD	SED	t	Significance
Emotional Intelligence	114	69.25	17.59	NA	NA	NA
Boys	52	67.48	18.42	3.401	0.47	Not Significant
Girls	62	65.88	17.68			
APL	84	65.97	15.44	3.922	1.766	Not significant
BPL	30	72.9	19.39			
General	77	65.10	16.12	3.792	1.323	Not Significant
Others	37	70.12	20.21			
Hindu	110	68.8	16.39	6.320	3.037	significant
Muslim	04	88	12.24			

H01- There is no significant difference exists between boys and girls in their emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Significant
Boys	52	67.48	18.42	0.47	Not Significant at 0.05 level
Girls	62	65.88	17.68		

Data Source: Author's calculation based on field survey 2025

Table-2: showed that the mean score of boys and girls students is 67.48 and 65.88 respectively. The standard deviations are 18.42 and 17.68 respectively. The calculated t-value is 0.47 which is not significant at 0.05 level i.e. there is no significant difference exists between boys and girls of their emotional intelligence. The null hypothesis will be unchanged.

H02-There is no significant difference exists between APL and BPL in their emotional intelligence of XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students.

Economic Status	N	Mean	SD	t	Significant
APL	84	65.97	15.44	1.766	Significant at 0.01 level
BPL	30	72.9	19.39		

Data Source: Author's calculation based on field survey 2025

Table-3: showed that the mean score of APL and BPL students is 65.97 and 72.9 respectively. The standard deviations are 15.44 and 19.39 respectively. The calculated t-value is 1.766 which is not significant at 0.05 level i.e. there is no significant difference exists between APL and BPL of their emotional intelligence. The null hypothesis will remain unchanged.

H03- There is no significant difference exists between general and others in their emotional intelligence of higher secondary school students.

Social Status	N	Mean	SD	t	Significant
General	77	65.10	16.12	1.323	Not Significant
Others	37	70.12	20.21		

Data Source: Author's calculation based on field survey 2025

Table-4: showed that the mean score of general and others students is 65.10 and 70.12 respectively. The standard deviations are 16.12 and 20.21 respectively. The calculated t-value is **1.323** which is not significant at 0.05 level i.e. there is no significant difference exists between general and others in terms of their emotional intelligence. The null hypothesis will remain unchanged.

H04- There is no significant difference exists between Hindu and others religion with respect to their Emotional Intelligence

Religion	N	Mean	SD	t	Significant
Hindu	110	68.8	16.399	3.037	significant
Muslim	04	88	12.24		

Data Source: Author's calculation based on field survey 2025

Table-5: showed that the mean score of Hindu and others religion students is 68.8 and 88 respectively. The standard deviations are 16.3.66 and 12.24 respectively. The calculated t-value is **3.037** which is significant at 0.05 level i.e. there is significant difference exists between general and others religion students in terms of their emotional intelligence. The null hypothesis is rejected.

Findings: After analyse and interpretation, it is clear that there is no significant difference found between APL and BPL, boys and girls, and general and others XIth & XIIth grade higher secondary school students in their emotional intelligence. Only significant difference exist between Hindu and others religion students.

Further suggestions

- Others areas of Paschim Medinipur district can be considered for comprehensive work.
- The time periods can be enlarged.
- Samples size can be enlarged.
- Many psychological variables can be taken into consideration.
- This study can be extended to different board students like CBSE, ICSE etc individually or altogether.
- This study can be conducted for others age group students (above19).
- Present study can be conducted to individual residing at others places and many parts of the world.

Educational implication:

The data analysis aids in determining the emotional intelligence of higher secondary school pupils. Students with low emotional intelligence scores need specialized counseling. In addition to improving

self-awareness, self-regulation, social skills, empathy, and motivation, this can assist teachers and students in developing the capacity to monitor their own and others' feelings and emotions. It also accomplishes educational goals and objectives

Conclusion: However, no significant difference was observed between boys & girls students, APL & BPL, general and others caste in terms of emotional intelligence. Only Hindu and others religion students have significant difference between them with respect to emotional intelligence,

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